

Supplementary

Table S1: List of the respective gene sets

mtDNA_rep	DNA_rep	ISR	PD_core	PD_assoc
ALKBH1	APEX1	AARS2	ATP13A2	ASXL3
APEX1	APEX2	ACOT11	CHCHD2	BAG3
BRCA1	APLF	APOE	DNAJC6	BIN3
CRY1	APTX	ASNS	EIF4G1	BRIP1
DNA2	BLM	ATF2	FBXO7	BST1
DUT	CETN2	ATF3	GBA1	C5orf24
ERCC2	DCLRE1A	ATF4	GIGYF2	CAB39L
ERCC6	DCLRE1C	ATF5	HTRA2	CAMK2D
LIG3	DDB1	ATF6	LRP10	CASC16
MGMT	DDB2	ATG5	LRRK2	CD19
MPG	ERCC1	BBC3	PARK7	CHD9
MUTYH	ERCC2	BGLAP	PINK1	CHRNA1
NEIL1	ERCC3	CA9	PLA2G6	CLCN3
NEIL2	ERCC4	CARS1	PRKN	CRHR1
NTHL1	ERCC5	CARS2	RIC3	CRLS1
OGG1	ERCC6	CASP12	SNCA	CTSB
PARK7	ERCC8	CCL2	SYNJ1	DLG2
PNKP	FAAP20	CCNA2	TMEM230	DNAH17
POLB	FEN1	CCND1	UCHL1	DYRK1A
POLG	GTF2H1	CDC42	USP24	ELOVL7
POLQ	GTF2H2	CEBPA	VPS13C	FAM171A2
PRIMPOL	GTF2H3	CEBPB	VPS35	FAM47E
RAD23A	GTF2H4	CEBPE		FAM47E-STBD1

RECQL4	GTF2H5	CHAC1		FAM49B
TP53BP1	H2AX	CREB1		FBRSL1
UNG	HPF1	CREBBP		FCGR2A
YBX1	LIG1	CSF1R		FGF20
	LIG3	CTNNB1		FYN
	LIG4	CXCL3		GAK
	MAD2L2	CXCL8		GALC
	MBD4	CYP2E1		GBF1
	MCMDC2	DARS2		GCH1
	MMS19	DDIT3		GPNUMB
	MPG	DDIT4		HIP1R
	MRE11	DDR2		HLA-DRB5
	MUTYH	DISC1		IGSF9B
	NAN1	DKK1		INPP5F
	NEIL1	DNAJB9		IP6K2
	NEIL2	DRD2		ITGA8
	NEIL3	EDN1		ITPKB
	NHEJ1	EIF2AK2		KCNIP3
	NTHL1	ELANE		KCNS3
	OGG1	ERBB2		KPNA1
	PARP1	ERVW-1		KRTCAP2
	PARP2	F7		LCORL
	PARP3	FGF19		LRRK2
	PARP9	FGF2		MAP4K4
	PNKP	FGF21		MBNL2
	POLA1	GNB1L		MCCC1
	POLB	GPT2		MED12L

	POLD1	HLA-DRB1		MEX3C
	POLD2	HMOX1		MIPOL1
	POLD3	HRK		NOD2
	POLD4	HSPA5		NUCKS1
	POLE	IARS1		PAM
	POLE2	IGFBP1		PMVK
	POLE3	IHH		RAB29
	POLE4	IL18		RETREG3
	POLH	IL1B		RIMS1
	POLI	IL23A		RIT2
	POLK	IL6		RNF141
	POLL	INHBE		RPS12
	POLM	INS		RPS6KL1
	POLN	IRF7		SATB1
	POLQ	ITIH3		SCAF11
	PRIMPOL	KAT2B		SCARB2
	PRKDC	KDM6B		SETD1A
	RAD1	LAMP3		SH3GL2
	RAD23A	LARS1		SIPA1L2
	RAD23B	LARS2		SNCA
	RAD50	LHX2		SPPL2B
	RAD9A	LITAF		SPTSSB
	RBX1	MAP1LC3B		STK39
	REV1	MCL1		SYT17
	REV3L	MTOR		TMEM163
	RFC4	NARS1		TMEM175
	RIF1	NARS2		TRIM40

	RNF168	NDC80		UBAP2
	RNF8	NFE2L2		UBTF
	SHLD1	NRP1		VAMP4
	SHLD2	NUPR1		VPS13C
	SHLD3	PDGFRA		WNT3
	SLX4	PENK		
	SMUG1	PER2		
	TDG	PLAT		
	TDP1	PLAU		
	TP53BP1	PMAIP1		
	UNG	POLR2C		
	UVSSA	PPARGC1A		
	XAB2	PPP1R15A		
	XPA	PRKN		
	XPC	PSEN1		
	XRCC1	PTGS2		
	XRCC4	PTH		
	XRCC5	RPS6KA3		
	XRCC6	RUNX2		
		S100A8		
		S100P		
		SARS2		
		SCG2		
		SERPINC1		
		SIGMAR1		
		SIRT1		
		SIRT2		

		SIRT4		
		SLC38A2		
		SLC6A4		
		SLC7A11		
		SNCG		
		SP7		
		SQSTM1		
		STAT3		
		TARS2		
		TH		
		THEG		
		TNC		
		TNF		
		TNFRSF10B		
		TNFRSF11A		
		TNFSF11		
		TRIB3		
		TRPV6		
		USF1		
		VEGFA		
		VIM		
		WARS2		
		YARS2		